

Features/Columns Name	Category	Description / Question	Coding / Response Options
consent	Demographics	Agreement to participate in the survey.	Binary: Yes
gender	Demographics	Participant's gender.	Categorical: Male, Female, Other
age	Demographics	Participant's age in years.	Numeric (Integer) > 16
relationship	Demographics	Relationship status.	Categorical: Single, Married, Divorced, Widowed, In a Relationship, Other
location	Demographics	Type of residential area.	Categorical: Urban, Semi-Urban, Rural
division	Demographics	Administrative division of Bangladesh.	Categorical: Dhaka, Chittagong, Rajshahi, Khulna, Barisal, Sylhet, Rangpur, Mymensingh
education	Demographics	Highest level of educational qualification.	Ordinal: Under Matric, SSC, HSC, Bachelor, Masters
ssc_gpa	Academics	Secondary School Certificate (SSC) GPA.	Numeric (0-5)
hsc_gpa	Academics	Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC) GPA.	Numeric (0-5)
current_year	Academics	Current year of study for students.	Categorical: Year 1, Year 2, Year 3, Year 4, Other
bachelor_cgpa	Academics	Bachelor's Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA).	Numeric (0-4)
master_cgpa	Academics	Master's Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA).	Numeric (0-4)
academic_satisfaction	Academics	Satisfaction with academic performance.	Ordinal: Happy, Neutral, Unhappy
job_type	Employment	Type of employment.	Categorical: Govt, Private, NGO, Self-employed
profession	Employment	Participant's profession.	Text (Open-ended)
salary	Employment	Monthly salary.	Numeric (Integer)
job_satisfaction	Employment	Satisfaction with current job.	Ordinal: High, Medium, Low
accommodation	Socioeconomic	Type of accommodation.	Categorical: Rented, Own, Hostel, Mess, Hall
family_members	Socioeconomic	Number of members in the family.	Numeric (Integer)
family_conflicts	Socioeconomic	Frequency of conflicts or quarrels in the family.	Binary: Yes, No
dependents	Socioeconomic	Number of dependents.	Numeric (Integer)
debt_status	Socioeconomic	Current debt status.	Ordinal: None, Moderate, High
loan_type	Socioeconomic	Type of loan, if any.	Categorical: Personal Loan, Mortgage, etc.
financial_stress	Socioeconomic	Level of financial stress.	Ordinal: Low, Medium, High, Very High
migration_status	Socioeconomic	Migration status.	Categorical: Rural→Urban, Local, None
climate_stress	Socioeconomic	Stress experienced due to climate change.	Ordinal: None, Moderate, Severe
screen_time	Lifestyle & Behaviors	Average hours of screen time per day.	Numeric (Decimal)
sleep_hours	Lifestyle & Behaviors	Average hours of sleep per day.	Numeric (Decimal)
physical_activity	Lifestyle & Behaviors	Frequency of physical activity.	Ordinal: Never, Rarely, Weekly, Daily
diet_pattern	Lifestyle & Behaviors	General diet pattern.	Categorical: Balanced, Irregular, Junk
phq9_interest	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Little interest or pleasure in doing things.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_depressed	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_sleep	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Trouble with sleep (too little, too much).	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_tired	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Feeling tired or having little energy.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_appetite	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Poor appetite or overeating.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_self_bad	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Feeling bad about yourself or like a failure.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_concentrate	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Trouble concentrating on things.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_movement	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Moving/speaking slowly or being fidgety/restless.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
phq9_suicidal	PHQ-9 (Depression)	Thoughts of being better off dead or self-harm.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
gad7_nervous	GAD-7 (Anxiety)	Feeling nervous, anxious, or on edge.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
gad7_worry_control	GAD-7 (Anxiety)	Not being able to stop or control worrying.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
gad7_excess_worry	GAD-7 (Anxiety)	Worrying too much about different things.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day

gad7_relax	GAD-7 (Anxiety)	Trouble relaxing.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
gad7_restless	GAD-7 (Anxiety)	Being so restless it is hard to sit still.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
gad7_irritable	GAD-7 (Anxiety)	Becoming easily annoyed or irritable.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
gad7_afraid	GAD-7 (Anxiety)	Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen.	Likert [0-3]: 0=Not at all, 1=Several days, 2=More than half the days, 3=Nearly every day
pss10_upset	PSS-10 (Stress)	Been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_uncontrol	PSS-10 (Stress)	Felt that you were unable to control important things in your life?	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_stressed	PSS-10 (Stress)	Felt nervous and 'stressed'?	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_confident_rev	PSS-10 (Stress)	Felt confident about your ability to handle personal problems? (reverse-scored)	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_going_way_rev	PSS-10 (Stress)	Felt that things were going your way? (reverse-scored)	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_cope	PSS-10 (Stress)	Found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_irritations_rev	PSS-10 (Stress)	Been able to control irritations in your life? (reverse-scored)	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_on_top_rev	PSS-10 (Stress)	Felt that you were on top of things? (reverse-scored)	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_angered	PSS-10 (Stress)	Been angered because of things outside your control?	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
pss10_difficulties	PSS-10 (Stress)	Felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	Likert [0-4]: 0=Never, 1=Almost never, 2=Sometimes, 3=Fairly often, 4=Very often
ace_insult	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Emotional Abuse: Did a parent often swear at, insult, or put you down?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_physical	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Physical Abuse: Did a parent often push, grab, slap, or throw something at you?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_injury	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Severe Physical Abuse: Did a parent ever hit you so hard that you had marks?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_sexual_touch	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Sexual Abuse: Did anyone ever touch or fondle you sexually?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_sex_attempt	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Sexual Abuse: Did anyone ever attempt to have sex with you?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_no_protection	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Emotional Neglect: Did you often feel you had no one to protect you?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_neglect	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Physical Neglect: Did you often feel you didn't have enough to eat or wear?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_parents_separated	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Household Dysfunction: Were your parents separated or divorced?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_domestic_violence	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Household Dysfunction: Was your mother often a victim of violence?	Binary: Yes, No
ace_household_issue	ACE (Adverse Childhood Experiences)	Household Dysfunction: Lived with anyone who was a problem drinker, drug user, etc.?	Binary: Yes, No
iat_online_longer	Digital Addiction (IAT)	How often do you stay online longer than you intended?	Likert [1-5]: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
iat_neglect_chores	Digital Addiction (IAT)	How often do you neglect chores to spend more time online?	Likert [1-5]: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
iat_prefer_internet	Digital Addiction (IAT)	How often do you prefer the excitement of the internet to intimacy?	Likert [1-5]: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
iat_online_relations	Digital Addiction (IAT)	How often do you form new relationships with fellow online users?	Likert [1-5]: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
iat_grades_suffer	Digital Addiction (IAT)	How often do your grades or schoolwork suffer?	Likert [1-5]: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
iat_offline_restless	Digital Addiction (IAT)	How often do you feel restless or irritable when offline?	Likert [1-5]: 1=Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Always
substance_tobacco	Substance Use	Frequency of tobacco use.	Ordinal: Never, Monthly, Weekly, Daily
substance_drug	Substance Use	Frequency of illicit drug use.	Ordinal: Never, Monthly, Weekly, Daily
suicidality_wish	Suicidality	Have you wished you were dead?	Binary: Yes, No
suicidality_intent	Suicidality	Have you had the intent to end your life?	Binary: Yes, No
suicidality_plan	Suicidality	Have you made any plans to commit suicide?	Binary: Yes, No
suicidality_attempt	Suicidality	Have you ever attempted suicide in the past?	Binary: Yes, No
access_counseling	Help-Seeking	Access to counseling services.	Binary: Yes, No
stigma_counseling	Help-Seeking	Perception of stigma for seeking counseling.	Binary: Yes, No
help_peers	Help-Seeking	Frequency of seeking help from peers for stress.	Ordinal: Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Often, Always
help_professional	Help-Seeking	Frequency of seeking professional help for stress.	Ordinal: Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Often, Always